

COMPOSITION AND PRINCIPLES OF MARKETING ELEMENTS

Razakov Babirmirza Ramazan ugli

Chief specialist of the Ministry of Agriculture

Rashidova Dildora Rasul kizi

Hamkorkbank Tashkent branch employee

In order to achieve the goal set in the marketing system, marketing tools, that is, a set of marketing methods and methods, are necessary to influence customers and other subjects. One of such tools is marketing mix, marketing complex. In 1964, Harvard Business School professor Neil Borden was the first to include them in the marketing theory. In this model, the marketing complex in the training system of marketers is called 4 "R" and was proposed by McCarthy in 1960. Four main elements of marketing are distinguished in this model: product, price, place, and promotion.

In the process of satisfaction of needs and wants through exchange in marketing activities, a person is definitely involved. That's why the 5 R's are included in the above-mentioned marketing elements, and it is emphasized that they are people. Marketing mix elements are shown in Figure 1.

1. - figure Marketing - mix elements.

In 1968, F. Kotler added public relations and politics to the marketing mix elements and expanded the previous 4 "R" to 6 "R".

Despite the limited use of the 4 "R" model, it plays a leading role in the development of marketing theory and practice.

Marketing complex is the adaptation of the firm to the market situation as measures of market influence and practical tools. A good marketing mix leads the company to occupy a good position in the market.

The classic marketing complex includes 4 elements and carries the name of the 4 "R" model:

- commodity (product);
- price (price);
- sale or movement of goods (plase);
- promotion or communications.

However, this view of a firm's marketing activities is somewhat limited: it is more product oriented than consumer oriented.

Therefore, in the 1980s, the marketing mix increased by 2 elements and was called the 6 "R" de b.

6 "R" model includes:

- commodity (product);
- price (price);
- sale or movement of goods (plase);
- promotion.
- employees (personnel);
- manner of action.

new model , the main focus is on the strategic aspect of marketing activities. However, after the emergence of the concept of internal and external consumers at the end of the 20th century, there was information about a new extension of the previous model. In 1999, John Baller introduced the 10 "R" model.

John Baller's new expanded marketing mix is called the corporate marketing mix.

10 "R" model includes the following elements:

1. philosophy - organizational philosophy - idea ;
2. personality - an employee who supports the necessary Farming philosophy;
3. people - human;
4. products - goods;
5. prices - prices;
6. place - place of residence ;
7. promotion - promotion;
8. performance - assessment-performance of agricultural activity ;
9. perception - feeling ;
10. positioning - positioning.

In marketing theory, the elements of the marketing complex have been established by scientists based on different approaches. The following table shows the results of the research of various scientists regarding the elements of the modern marketing complex.

Table 1

Elements of modern marketing complex

Model name	Structural structure	Author
5 R	4R + Packaging	DJ. T. Rfssel, URLane
5R	4R+ Preception	N. Hart
6R	4R + Public opinion + Politics	F. Kotler
7R	4R + People + Process + Physical Evidence (conditions, company style)	Y. Ellwood
8R	7R +Pace (time compatibility)	L. Tweed
12R	8R +Permission (freedom in communication)+Paradigm (creating new rules)+Pass along (direct marketing (word of mouth))+Practice (experience)	S. Godin

The marketing mix in its most common form includes 4 marketing submixes. These are: product mix, contract mix, distribution mix, communication mix.

The product mix forms the product policy, includes measures related to the product. These measures are: design, decoration, product quality, packaging, customer service, warranty policy, etc.

In the contract mix, it is envisaged to meet the terms of the act of sale of goods and their formalization in the form of a transaction. These measures include: price policy, markup and discount system, terms of goods delivery and payment, as well as credit policy.

The distribution mix includes the delivery of goods to the final recipient at the place of production. This policy includes sales channel justification and analysis, marketing logistics, sales policy, sales force policy, production force deployment policy, customer and market location policy, delivery policy, finished goods warehousing policy, etc. .

The task of the communicative mix is to organize the interaction of all the objects of the marketing system with the Farmers - the producers of the products in order to satisfy the needs of the customer and to generate the demand and to provide an alternative and effective activity in moving the goods and services.

Marketing objectives are divided into four alternative objectives in terms of social importance:

1. Increasing the level of consumption;

2. Maximize customer satisfaction;
3. Maximizing consumer choice;
4. Improving lifestyle (quality).

An increase in the level of consumption leads to an increase in the profits of producers, to the development of production and the service sector, and also to a decrease in consistency.

Maximizing customer satisfaction aims to achieve full compliance with the properties of the product (service) expected by the consumer.

Maximizing consumer choice shows consumers a variety of such goods (services) and embodies goods that can be searched for goods in a perfectly suitable market for their employees.

In improving the quality of life, marketing does not mean the sale of goods, quality assurance, and product (service) being acceptable in terms of price, but physical and material quality.

Basic principles of marketing:

1. Consumer orientation;
2. Future orientation. The manufacturer should aim at long-term results, not short-term results;
3. Orientation to achieve the last practical results.

The result of marketing activities should be measurable (market share, sales volume, profit growth).

Marketing principles are a condition, a requirement that reveals the basis of marketing and its essence. The essence of marketing is the production of goods and customer service, demand, and the constant targeting of production capabilities to market demand.

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